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From roads to the air: The role of asphalt pavements on urban air quality

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Macroscopic surfaces and urban air quality

Global population is growing, and increasingly concentrated in cities: **56% today, > 70% by 2050**

Macroscopic surfaces
60 – 90 % of the total surface of an urban site!

What is their role on urban air quality climate?

The importance of asphalt pavements as pollutant sources

Asphalt pavements corresponds to around 40-60% of the area of an urban city, a percentage that keeps increasing with urbanization.¹

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A chemically interesting material to deal with!

Composition: ca. 5% w/w bitumen, 95% w/w of filler.

- Asphalt/bitumen is a petroleum byproduct, composed of a large number of organic species. **Hydrocarbons (alkanes, alkenes, aromatics,...)** **Heteroatoms**, such as S (0-9% wt.), N (0-2% wt.), and O (0-2% wt.),

Temperature, humidity, sunlight radiation impact the physicochemical properties of the material and thus their emission efficiency.

¹ Akbari, H., et al. *Landsc. Urban Plan.* **2003**, *63* (1), 1.

² Joy H. Tannous and Arno de Klerk, *Energy & Fuels*, 2019, *33*, 7083–7093

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Overall, what is the long term impact of asphalt pavement on urban air quality under service temperature?

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How can a macroscopic surface impact air quality?

Objectives of our studies in IMT Nord Europe

Laboratory experiments inside highly instrumented atmospheric simulation chambers

The Observation phase

- 1 *VOCs emission Factors*
Determine the VOC & iVOC **emissions from conventional fresh / aged** asphalt pavements VS atmospheric condition (temperature, humidity, sunlight radiation)

- Mostly studied in literature
- More work is currently undergoing!

- 2 *Secondary pollutant formation*
Evaluate the ability of **asphalt pavements** to act as a **source** of secondary pollutants (SOA)

- Challenging! Not thoroughly evaluated!
- New developed protocols for accurate air quality assessments!

- 3 *Uptake of pollutants on asphalt pavements*
Evaluate the ability of **asphalt pavements** to act as a **sink** of atmospheric pollutants

- Asphalt as a surface, react with the atmospheric pollutants
- Overlooked in the literature!
 - Ignored in atmospheric science & modeling!

Atmospheric simulation chamber to study asphalt pavements emissions

The **mini-THALAMOS** experimental set-up

Results and Discussion: Temperature dependence of VOCs emissions

- A list of 20 masses/compounds contribute to more than 80% of total emissions detected.
- The temperature increase lead to an increase to the emissions of the same compounds.

Results and Discussion: Impact of RH and light irradiation to VOCs emissions

Compared to dark and dry:

- EFs increased by a factor of 9 with **RH**. **Change in the physical properties of the material. Diffusion of polar compounds on the surface of the material**
- EFs increased by a factor of 6 under **UV-Vis irradiation** of the surface **photolysis of surface species ? Photochemistry at the air surface interface?**
- EFs increased by a factor of 20 under **UV-Vis irradiation and humid conditions. synergy between the abovementioned effects?**

Synergetic effect of light and RH enhance VOCs emissions from asphalt pavements

Results and Discussion: First evaluation of impacts on air quality

From the **measured** VOC emissions to the asphalt pavement **impact** on air quality

Lab experiments

Determined emission factors
20 most emitted VOCs

20% of road transport
& 3% of total VOCs

City scale model

Input data
to estimate the impacts
& make predictions

Results on ozone &
SOA formation
Up to 6% of SOA (PM₁)

Air quality
assessment

The case of Paris

Today: VOCs emitted from asphalt pavements is a **significant source of VOCs in urban areas**, highly dependent of atmospheric conditions.

Future (2030-2050): The anticipated reduction of vehicle emissions makes asphalt pavements as the dominant source of air pollution in urban environments.

pubs.acs.org/estair

Article

Real-World Asphalt Pavement Emissions: Combining Simulation Chamber Measurements and City Scale Modeling to Elucidate the Impacts on Air Quality

Published as part of ACS ES&T Air special issue "John H. Seinfeld Festschrift".

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Cite This: <https://doi.org/10.1021/acsestair.4c00323>

Read Online

But how reliable are model simulations? How can we really improve their estimations?

VOCS in urban areas, highly dependent of atmospheric conditions.

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Approach to estimate the impacts on air quality

Traditional approach

New approach! Reliable & Fast!

Atmospheric simulation chamber for asphalt emissions oxidation

Case study 1: Reproducing daytime photo-oxidation scenarios in the chamber using real world pavements

Particles formation potential and air quality simulations

Estimations presented are based on daily average values, summed over Paris city center

General remarks:

- Fine and ultrafine particles formation (<PM₁, harmful for humans)
- SOA formation rate increases exponentially with surface temperature
- A generic expression is produced, to describe the

$$\text{SOA formation rate } (\mu\text{g s}^{-1} \text{m}^{-2}) : 4.9 \times 10^{-2} + 1.94 \times 10^{-13} T^{(6.70 \pm 2.24)}$$

Particles emitted from asphalt pavements contribute to more than 14% of the total particulate matter over the Paris city center

Atmospheric simulation chambers as prediction tool for air pollution reduction

Case study 2: oxidation of asphalt cocktail pollutants reproducing daytime or nighttime scenarios.

Asphalt cocktail injected in the chamber and oxidized

- Fluoranthene
- Anthracene
- 1-Methyl naphthalene
- Quinoline
- Benzothiophene
- Triethylene glycol
- 9-Hydroxyfluorene
- Salicylic acid
- Catechol
- Dibenzofuran
- 2,3-Dihydrobenzofuran
- Benzofuran
- Toluene

Ultrafine particles formation

Elimination of catechol can reduce ultrafine formation by more than > 90%

Simulation chambers are diagnostic tool for secondary pollution elimination

Foreseen the future - perspectives

The Observation phase

1

Determine the VOCs and iVOCs **emissions of conventional fresh / aged** asphalt pavements Vs atmospheric condition (temperature, humidity, sunlight radiation)

2

Evaluate the ability of **asphalt pavements** to act as a **source** of secondary pollutants (SOA)

3

Evaluate the ability of **asphalt pavements** to act as a **sink** of atmospheric pollutants.

The Action phase

How can we prepare atmospherically friendly materials?

Determine the VOCs and iVOCs **emissions of novel eco-friendly proposed materials** (recycled, bio-based, etc) Vs Temperature, humidity, sunlight radiation

Reduce the ability of **novel materials** to act as a **source** of secondary pollutants (SOA)

Evaluate the ability of **novel materials** to act as a **sink** of atmospheric pollutants. Use asphalt as depolluting surface in urban environments.

Atmospheric modeling